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Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

Initial exploration of queer marriage dynamics during the first year of partnership. Examines transition from dating to married life, renegotiating boundaries, and establishing shared values. Discusses clinical considerations for LGBTQ+ couples creating marital structures that honor both individual identity and collective partnership. Addresses unique challenges and strengths in queer marital formation.

Keywords

relationships, LGBTQ+, identity

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